

Pedagogical Foundations Important for Training Future Speech Therapists

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Abstract

This article discusses the relevance of issues related to speech defects that shape human thinking, their types and stages, as well as technologies. The mechanisms of the field of critical thinking are also highlighted.

Keywords Critical thinking, critical thinking style, balance between information, internal experiences, and the external world.

Introduction

Today, our society demands individuals who can rebuild quickly and create ideas to find a way out of difficult situations. The deep changes taking place in modern education set the use of new technologies in teaching and upbringing as a priority task. According to pedagogues, they have the opportunity to choose the most optimal teaching methods and technologies for constructing and designing the learning process. The aim of the technology for developing critical thinking is to enhance students' intellectual abilities that are not only necessary in education but also in later life (the ability to make precise decisions, work with information, analyze different aspects of events), and so on.

Main Part

Forming students' critical thinking skills depends on organizing lessons using educational technologies by higher education faculty and creating favorable conditions for them to learn independently. Today, our pedagogues and parents are required not only to pay particular attention to the education and upbringing of the youth but also to engage more in conversations with them and encourage their critical thinking. In this regard, several reforms are being implemented in the education sector of our country. Examples include the Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5847 "On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" dated October 8, 2019, the Presidential Resolution No. PQ-4199 "On Measures to Establish Presidential Schools" dated February 20, 2019, and the Presidential Resolution No. PQ-4884 "On Additional Measures to Further Improve the Education System" dated November 6, 2020, which serve the purpose of further developing and improving the education system.

J. Braus and D. Wund define critical thinking as reflective thinking aimed at determining what to believe and what to do. According to them, it is the sharpness of intelligence, which reflects the ability to objectively think and act logically while taking into account their viewpoints and those of others, as well as to abandon their misconceptions. The technology of critical thinking emerged in the 1980s in America. In Russia, this technology has been known since the late 1990s under a different name—"Reading and Writing for Critical Thinking."

L.S. Vygotsky wrote about the intrinsic connection between the zone of proximal development, learning, and the general development of a child; K. Popper and R. Paul discussed the foundations of forming and developing critical thinking; E. Brown and I. Beck focused on metacognitive education. Developers of the KM technology, Curtis Meredith, Charles Temple, and Ginni Steele, translated the rules of these theories into practical language, brought their work to the level of pedagogical technology, and distinguished its stages, methodological techniques, and criteria. Therefore, numerous teachers can use their developments in their work, achieving effective results. Thus, critical thinking is not a separate skill but rather a set of many skills and abilities that gradually form in a child during their development and educational process.

If children are not passive listeners during lessons but instead actively seek information and connect what they learn to their practical experiences, critical thinking skills will form more quickly. Moreover, students should question the reliability of information, examine the logic of arguments, draw conclusions, create new examples to apply theoretical knowledge, make decisions, and study their causes and consequences (teachers must assist in this). Systematically introducing critical thinking into the educational process should form a distinct way of thinking and cognitive activity. The uniqueness of this pedagogical technology lies in the fact that the student constructs this process independently during the educational process, based on real and specific goals, monitors its developmental trajectory, and determines the final result. On the other hand, using this strategy aims to develop skills for thoughtful working with information. To enable children to actively work with the knowledge they acquire, the authors of the technology suggest building the lesson according to the usual scheme: "introduction - main part - conclusion." Within the framework of the technology, these stages acquire slightly different names and functions.

The Technology for Forming Critical Thinking Includes:

- Emphasizing the search for knowledge and independent assimilation;
- Actively using students' previous experiences and knowledge;
- Encouraging the expression of one's viewpoint, position, and exchange of thoughts at all levels of interaction;
- Creating conditions for substantiating conclusions, judgments, and positions;
- Encouraging attempts to test and apply new knowledge and experience.

Human Thinking and Its Significance: Thinking is a spiritual quality of human activity, its own power, strength, and composition. The development of thinking is an essential driving force of socio-economic progress; hence, the history of thought is closely related to human relations and the fundamental principles determining life. In the early stages of human creation, thought was in the form of understanding natural processes, using them for survival, and protecting oneself. Thus, human thought developed, and other material-spiritual aspects of human labor began to emerge. What is thought? Thought is the interconnection and development of meanings in the human mind. We provide the most modern definition of thought. The stages of thought consist of understanding, reflection, consciousness, and thinking. Consciousness consists of three elements: clarity of thought,

reflection, and understanding. The power of thought is its scientific nature, depth, ornament (nobility and dedication to purpose), and breadth. The purity of thought is its focus on a specific field. There are chronological, problematic, hypothetical, heuristic, inductive, and other types of thinking. In general, if thought types are systematized, they can be divided into cause and effect logical thinking. The great pedagogue A. Avloni wrote about the education of thought: "The education of thought is a sacred duty that has been respected for a long time, entrusted to the attention of teachers, and burdened on their conscience. The power, ornament, and breadth of thought depend on the teacher's upbringing." Our President I. Karimov, in an interview with the editor-in-chief of the journal "Tafakkur," said, "If children do not learn free thinking, the outcome of the given education is bound to be low." Therefore, for a person to lead a meaningful life, they must first learn about the reality surrounding them and possess high intellect and experience. Because intellect holds an essential place in a person's life, only through intelligence can one achieve wisdom, deep thought, honesty, righteousness, foresight, and avoidance of base desires.

The Positive Solution to a Problem Depends Not Only on New Ideas But Also on Their Practicality: Through this skill, we evaluate ideas and thoughts, select the best ones, and use them to change our lives. A person who thinks critically understands ideas and thoughts well. As a result, they understand the world better and faster than others. For instance, if you disagree with your friends' opinions about an object, you may begin to doubt their assumptions, attempt to prove the validity of your doubts, explore, and achieve success. This is an example of critical thinking. Critical thinking is the ability to use information clearly and logically to solve a problem and to acquire additional information when needed. The primary content of the works carried out based on the Decree of President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev No. PF-5812, "On Additional Measures for Further Improvement of the Vocational Education System," dated September 6, 2019, aims to create future personnel and continuously develop the conditions for forming their professional skills to conduct professional activities. It aims to improve the vocational education system on the basis of advanced foreign experience, introduce stages of primary, secondary, and specialized vocational education, prepare qualified and competitive personnel for the labor market, and involve employers extensively in this process.

A Person with Critical Thinking Skills:

- Uses evidence rationally and impartially;
- Expresses their thoughts clearly and consistently;
- Distinguishes illogical conclusions from invalid ones;
- Does not rush to make decisions if there is insufficient evidence.

For example, an employee of a company fails to complete a task on time. The manager must punish them. However, a critically thinking manager does not rush to make a decision.

Conclusion

They first analyze the consequences of the decision and evaluate the correctness of their actions. A person with critical thinking skills has a high inclination toward independent learning. In this case, we enrich our knowledge, feel the need for additional information, and seek it out. Forming critical thinking skills in students is advisable for properly analyzing questions that arise during career choice. Through critical thinking, a person can control and manage the balance between their inner experiences and the external world. Based on critical thinking, students can accurately assess their interests and abilities and evaluate themselves. This is an important factor in the career selection

process. Along with choosing the profession they are interested in, students will also identify and understand the sources of knowledge necessary for their chosen careers.

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